

Improving Liver Tumor Classification in MRI Images using CoAtNet: A Deep Learning Model

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Abstract: For effective clinical management and enhanced patient outcomes, accurate and timely detection of liver tumors is important. Deep learning (DL) plays an increasingly crucial role in the categorization of hepatic tumors. DL is anticipated to play a larger role in medical image processing as it continues to develop. This research presents a novel CoAtNet model for the binary classification of liver tumors based on contrast-enhanced MRI (CE-MRI) images. Using the "A Tumour and Liver Automatic Segmentation" (ATLAS) data set, which systematically annotates liver tumors on hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) CE-MRI scans, the model demonstrates outstanding performance. The input data for deep learning are optimized by extensive data preprocessing, including image standardization, pixel value normalization, and data type conversion. In addition, data augmentation techniques, such as flipping and rotation, considerably enlarge the dataset, thereby enhancing the model's generalizability. Based on transfer learning from the ImageNet dataset, the CoAtNet model demonstrates exceptional accuracy, f1-score, sensitivity, precision, and specificity, making it a reliable tool for early liver cancer diagnosis. The proposed model obtained an accuracy of 99.20%, an f1-score of 98.95%, a sensitivity of 98.56%, a precision of 99.12%, and a specificity of 99.27%. This research can advance the treatment and diagnosis of liver cancer.

Keywords: Liver tumor, Hepatocellular carcinoma, Deep learning, CoAtNet, ATLAS dataset, MRI images.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, medical imaging modalities, like MRI, ultrasound (US), computed tomography (CT), mammography, positron emission tomography (PET), and X-ray, have played a crucial part in the early identification, treatment, and diagnosis of disease. In liver image-related tasks, the incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly DL, has arisen as a highly promising tool. This technology has tremendous potential for improving the detection and evaluation of liver lesions, expediting clinical therapy for liver-related conditions, and even predicting treatment responses.

The identification, classification, and diagnosis of tumorous structures within organs rely heavily on medical imaging, which provides a less invasive alternative to biopsies. It provides healthcare professionals with a rapid and reliable method for assessing lesions, with a focus on detecting metastases, particularly in cases of HCC. CT, MRI, and US are commonly used imaging modalities for hepatic lesions. CT and MRI stand out among these imaging modalities as the preferable options for liver screening, detection, and classification. Their superiority resides in their increased specificity and sensitivity in comparison to other methods. CT and MRI images offer superior resolution and clarity, outperforming the US.

Consequently, diagnoses based on CT and MRI scans provide a higher level of precision in differentiating between healthy and unhealthy patients and in identifying various diseases. MRI is more effective than CT at characterizing minor lesions (3 cm) and is frequently used as a complementary modality to CT. T2-weighted imaging typically reveals liver lesion tissues to be hyperintense or hypointense relative to the adjacent parenchyma. However, relying solely on T2-weighted imaging may not always be adequate, as certain lesions may still appear hypointense. Diffusion-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging (DW-MRI) is utilized for a more comprehensive characterization of liver lesions, presenting valuable information into tumor viability at the cell level and aiding in the differentiation of HCC from

dysplastic nodules. CE-MRI outperforms DW-MRI when it comes to the detection and characterization of HCC, providing superior capabilities.

A significant global health burden, liver tumors rank sixth in terms of diagnosis prevalence and third in terms of cancer-related mortality. According to data from the World Health Organization for the year 2020, there were 905,677 newly diagnosed cases of liver cancer and 830,180 fatalities. There were 34,743 new cases of liver cancer and 33,793 deaths in India in the same year. According to these statistics, the liver tumor is the tenth most prevalent cancer in India, with the eighth greatest mortality rate. Notably, HCC emerged as the primary cause of cancer-related mortality among both men and women in multiple countries, including Mongolia, Thailand, Cambodia, Egypt, and Guatemala, among 18 others. In another 18 countries, HCC was the leading cause of cancer-related fatalities among men, highlighting its global impact [4]. HCC continues to contribute significantly to both cancer incidence and mortality rates. Despite substantial research efforts and the development of new treatment modalities, the prognosis for individuals with HCC remains dismal.

Figure 1. Liver Tumor Types in MRI

As depicted in Figure 1, liver tumors can be divided into six distinct varieties. Hepatocellular Adenoma (HCA), Hemangioma, Cyst, HCC, Hepatoblastoma, and Metastasis. Among these, HCA is a common tumor in liver cancer instances. Malignant liver tumors include HCC, hepatoblastoma, and metastases, whereas benign

liver tumors include HCA, hemangiomas, and cysts. Based on their histological nature and behaviour, this classification helps distinguish and characterize the various varieties of liver tumors.

In recent years, the use of AI technology in medical research has increased dramatically, and the field of HCC is no exception. Deep learning algorithms are recognized as advanced techniques among the variety of AI-based algorithms, as they are capable of efficiently managing and processing complex multimodal data. These data sources range from routine clinical variables to medical images with high resolution. Deep learning introduces a revolutionary change by exchanging manually designed feature filters with architecture for representation learning. This method operates the input data via multiple transformation layers, each of which contains nonlinear elements. As the data moves through these layers, the features are gradually learned and represented, culminating in the extraction of high-level features constructed on the foundation of lower-level ones. Particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), artificial intelligence has proven useful in image interpretation, which includes disciplines such as pathology and radiology. This technology possesses promising diagnostic potential for HCC and liver masses.

Deep transfer learning techniques have gained traction in medical image processing, as they offer the benefit of training network weights on large datasets and fine-tuning them on smaller datasets. Using MRI images, this research introduces a deep transfer learning model, the CoAtNet-7 architecture, for the classification and detection of liver lesions. Implementation of the model in MATLAB and experimental evaluation are performed to classify liver lesions from MRI images. Notably, the ATLAS dataset used in this work has already been segmented, eliminating the need for segmentation tasks prior to use and expediting the classification procedure.

This research aims to address the critical challenge of accurate HCC detection from MRI liver images, a pressing global health issue associated with substantial morbidity and mortality. The work centers on developing and evaluating a deep

transfer learning model, CoAtNet-7, a binary classification model implemented for liver tumor classification and detection. The scope includes the use of a preprocessed and segmented MRI liver dataset as well as extensive experimentation to evaluate the model's efficacy. In the field of medical image processing, the research evaluates performance using metrics such as accuracy, f1-score, sensitivity, precision, and specificity and compares the proposed model with existing approaches; this improves early-stage HCC diagnosis and patient outcomes.

The following are the primary objectives of this research:

- To identify the malignant liver tumor using the CoAtNet, a pre-trained classification model.
- To utilize the proposed transfer learning method for extracting the features utilizing its learned weights from the ImageNet data set.
- To perform extensive tests on liver tumor MRI images to determine the proposed model's efficiency.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed model in classifying liver tumor.
- To assess the performance of the research model in terms of accuracy, f1-score, sensitivity, precision, and specificity.
- To compare the proposed model with existing approaches in liver tumor classification, highlighting its advantages and limitations.

This section of the introduction discusses liver tumor and the types of tumors that can be detected using MRI imaging. The following are the sections that will be covered next. Specifically, Section 2 discusses related works done on the classification and detection of liver tumor. Section 3 presents the ATLAS dataset, data augmentation and the proposed CoAtNet architecture in detail, Section 4 represents the experimental results and analysis, and Section 5 presents a conclusion and recommendations for future directions.

2. Related Works

A CNN-based deep learning algorithm for HCC detection in liver Dynamic CE-MRI (DCE-MRI) sequences was proposed in. This study developed a parallel preprocessing algorithm that aided in the detection and localization of HCC in MRI images using a CNN model. Using MRI patches, the algorithm detected HCC with 90% accuracy in both arterial and portal phases. Additional semantic techniques could have been incorporated into the detection process to enhance the model.

Using contrast-enhanced MRI scans, evaluated the efficacy of a radiomics model and a deep learning model in distinguishing high-grade from low-grade liver tumors in 361 patients with hepatocellular carcinoma. Manual segmentation of lesions produced 426 training set lesions and 83 test set lesions. The radiomics model using SVM with feature selection outperformed the deep learning model, but its feature selection process was more complex. Based on DenseNet, the DenseNet-based deep learning model offered a simpler training method but marginally inferior performance. The advantages of the radiomics model in terms of computational cost and model interpretability emphasize the trade-offs between the two approaches for grading liver tumors using MR images.

Deep learning was used into automate the implementation of the Liver Imaging Reporting and Data System (LI-RADS) for HCC diagnosis. On multi-phasic CE-MRIs acquired utilizing T1-w sequences, a deep-CNN (DCNN) with a U-Net architecture was trained. Post-processing consisted of the random forest approach with radiomic features and mean neural activation thresholding (TR) to reduce false positives. The combination of random forest and thresholding with the U-Net improved performance, indicating the potential for enhancing workflow efficiency in liver lesion diagnosis within LI-RADS, which is presently dependent on manual delineation.

The potential of automated machine learning, specifically using the Tree-Based Pipeline Optimization Tool (TPOT) in Python, for differentiating hepatocellular carcinoma from intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma on multi-phasic MRI scans was

proposed in. Utilizing a genetic programming algorithm, TPOT automated crucial radiomics workflow steps to improve classification accuracy. The outcomes demonstrated that automated machine learning performed similarly to manual optimization, achieving specificity and sensitivity comparable to that of experts in distinguishing between the two liver malignancies. However, it had limitations in cases satisfying the LI-RADS category for LR-M, necessitating advanced research into classifier and feature selection methods.

Using dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI, unenhanced MRI images, and clinical data, developed a deep-learning CNN model for accurate liver tumor diagnosis using dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI and unenhanced MRI images. In classifying liver tumors into seven categories and distinguishing malignant from benign tumors using unenhanced images alone, the developed deep learning system outperformed experienced radiologists. The model showed promise for reducing the use of contrast agents, mitigating adverse effects, and reducing the cost of standard MRI exams for liver tumor patients.

A CNN model for classifying common liver tumor on multi-phased MRI scans was devised and validated in. On the basis of typical imaging characteristics, the CNN architecture trained with an Adam optimizer effectively classified six categories of hepatic lesions. This suggests that the DLS has the potential to provide a rapid and reliable "second opinion" to radiologists, facilitating the interpretation of challenging cases and reducing diagnostic variability for hepatic lesions.

The research in developed a hybrid model that combined a regularization functionality with the existing loss function of the SVM model to enhance the accuracy and processing time of liver tumor classification from MRI images. This method ranked image classes and utilized the region growing algorithm for ROI identification, Weiner filter for enhancing image, and the GLCM for features extraction. The SVM model then utilized these features for classifying affected regions

while excluding unwanted areas, improving accuracy and processing time for the early identification of liver tumors using MR images.

A deep learning model was devised into distinguish between non-HCC and HCC tumors on CE-MRI, including those with atypical characteristics. Using pathologically confirmed lesions as a reference, the model was intended to validate CNN's ability to manage a broader spectrum of non-HCC and HCC tumor on multi-phase MRI. While the accuracy was slightly lower than previous research focusing on classical lesions, this study demonstrated that a CNN trained with atypical tumors could yet distinguish among non-HCC and HCC tumors on CE-MRI scans with a relatively high degree of accuracy.

In, an automatic DL model for detecting HCC in hepatobiliary MRI images was developed. The model used a CNN structure with ReLU activation and the Adam optimizer. Notably, this deep learning system outperformed less experienced radiologists by detecting very small HCCs in gadoteric acid-enhanced MRI scans with greater precision. This development has the potential to enhance the early detection of HCC and improve patient outcomes in the fight against this prevalent and significant cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide.

A 3-D CNN model for medical imaging, specifically for differentiating between primary and metastatic liver lesions utilizing DW-MRI data, was proposed in. Designed to operate directly with 3D tomographic data, the 3-D CNN eliminates the need for preprocessing steps such as cropping, ROI annotation, and CAD detectors during training and validation. Using data augmentation techniques to resolve class imbalance in the dataset resulted in a significant improvement in tissue classification accuracy. This method could improve the characterization of liver carcinoma in medical imaging.

The classification and identification of liver carcinoma using image processing and machine learning have been presented. The fuzzy histogram equalization method was used to reduce image noise during the preprocessing phase, and the images were

segmented to focus on the area of interest. Three classification techniques, including RBF-SVM, ANN, and random forest, were used. The RBF-SVM algorithm excelled in precision and specificity for the classification of liver tumors. This study demonstrated the value of integrating image processing and machine learning to improve liver tumor detection and classification.

Using fused 2D CT and MRI images, the research in demonstrated the efficacy of machine learning (ML) for classifying liver cancer. Included in the preprocessing was noise reduction and automated ROI selection. The top 10 optimized hybrid features were identified through feature selection. Using tenfold cross-validation, four ML classifiers (MLP, SVM, RF, and J48) were evaluated for their ability to diagnose six liver tumor types accurately. This method is robust, efficient, and suitable for large clinical datasets, thereby reducing human error in diagnosis.

2.1. Analysis Summary

Extensive research has examined the application of ML and DL techniques to medical imaging, particularly MRI and CT scans, in the domain of liver tumor classification and identification. These analyses have demonstrated the ability of deep learning, radiomics models, and hybrid approaches to resolving the difficulty of accurate tumor identification. Results have emphasized the trade-offs between computational efficiency and model interpretability, highlighting the value of radiomics and DL models in grading liver tumors. In addition, efforts to automate systems such as LI-RADS and the implementation of automated machine learning have shown promise in streamlining the diagnosis of liver lesions. At the same time, custom CNN architectures have the potential to provide reliable supplementary radiologist support. The efficacy of hybrid models and deep learning systems has been demonstrated in the classification of liver tumors, including the differentiations of HCC from various liver tumors. The proposed research introduces a deep transfer learning model, CoAtNet-7, for binary HCC detection in liver MRI images, leveraging a pre-segmented dataset to

expedite the classification process and contribute to a more accurate early-stage HCC diagnosis in the domain of medical image processing.

3. Proposed Methodology

This section represents the systematic and structured approach to address the problem of HCC detection in liver MRI images using the CoAtNet-7 deep transfer learning model. This section outlines the key steps in data preprocessing, model implementation, training, and evaluation, which collectively form the framework for achieving the research objectives. The methodological approach is designed to leverage a pre-segmented MRI liver dataset and harness the power of state-of-the-art DL techniques, ultimately contributing to the enhanced early diagnosis of HCC, with significant implications for the field of medical image processing. As illustrated in Figure 2, the proposed research model begins with the input dataset, which consists of liver MRI images from the ATLAS dataset and serves as the primary data source for HCC detection. To facilitate deep learning, data preprocessing procedures are then applied, including image standardization, pixel value normalization, and consistent data type conversion.

Figure 2. Workflow of the Proposed Model

Data augmentation techniques, such as horizontal and vertical tilting and rotation, are utilized to augment the dataset and improve model robustness. The data set was then split into testing and training sets, which are essential for assessing the generalization performance of the model. The CoAtNet model, a deep transfer learning architecture pre-trained on a comprehensive data set such as ImageNet, is implemented and configured for binary classification, with the detection of HCC in liver MRI images as the specific objective. Subsequently, the model undergoes training using the training dataset, where it learns to recognize key patterns and features while modifying internal parameters to make accurate predictions. Adjustments to learning rates, batch sizes, and regularization techniques are made to optimize the model's efficacy via hyperparameter tuning. Following model training, the testing data set was utilized to evaluate the model's performance in detecting HCC in previously unseen images based on a variety of performance metrics. This phase is essential for comprehending the model's practical efficacy. The study concludes with a comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the results, highlighting the model's strengths, limitations, and prospective clinical relevance for HCC diagnosis within the field of medical image processing.

3.1. ATLAS Dataset

The ATLAS dataset is an invaluable resource in the field of medical imaging, especially for HCC diagnosis and liver tumor segmentation on CE-MRI scans. ATLAS is the only dataset accessible to the public that presents systematic labelling of liver malignancies in HCC CE-MRI images. It consists of a total of 90 CE-MRI scans, each of which focuses particularly on the liver, obtained from 90 patients with unresectable HCC. In addition, the dataset contains segmentation masks meticulously constructed for both liver and liver tumors. The ATLAS dataset provides essential metadata for each acquisition, such as image resolutions, MRI sequence, contrast phase, and MRI manufacturer, for comprehensive comprehension and analysis. The dataset has been

meticulously split into a training set including data from 60 patients and a testing set consisting of data from 30 patients. This allows for the evaluation and validation of models and algorithms developed utilizing this invaluable resource. The ATLAS dataset not only contributes to advances in medical image processing but also has the potential to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of liver tumor diagnosis and treatment planning in clinical practice.

Figure 3 showcases two axial slices from CE-MRI scans of liver tumors. The first image is from a CE-MRI scan of a patient with a tumor that has low contrast, making it less distinct from surrounding liver tissue. The second image features an annotated tumor label, indicating the precise region of the liver that contains the tumor.

3.2. Data Preprocessing

In the proposed research, data preprocessing procedures are crucial for prepping the input dataset of liver MRI images for deep learning. Image Standardization, Pixel Value Normalization, and Consistent Data Type Conversion are the processes involved in these procedures. Ensuring that all MRI images are converted to a standard format, including resolution and dimension consistency. The standardization facilitates the data input process for the CoAtNet-7 model and ensures that all images are processed under identical conditions, thereby making the model more effective and reliable. This phase involves resizing the ATLAS dataset's image resolution to a standard 224x224 pixel format. This operation is designed to make images compatible with the CoAtNet-7 model. By converting the image resolution to 224x224 pixels, the data becomes suitable for the model, as this resolution meets the model's specifications and permits optimal feature extraction. Typically, normalization involves scaling pixel values to a common range (e.g., [0, 1] or [-1, 1]) to reduce intensity level differences between images. This phase reduces the model's sensitivity to variations in image brightness and contrast, thereby enhancing its capacity to discover meaningful

features. In the data preprocessing procedures, the ATLAS dataset is converted from NIfTI (Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative) format to DICOM format. This conversion is necessary to ensure that all images are processed using a standard data format, thereby facilitating the compatibility and consistency required for deep learning. The data are made uniform and suitable for training the CoAtNet-7 model by converting the NIfTI images to DICOM.

Figure 3. Sample Images from Dataset

3.2.1. Data Augmentation

In the research, data augmentation is a critical process that enhances the training dataset by generating variations of the original images. In this case, two primary augmentation techniques are employed: flipping and rotation. Flipping involves creating mirror images of the original dataset.

There are four key orientations, as represented in Figure 4:

- **Original:** This represents the original image.
- **Horizontal Flip:** The image is flipped horizontally as if looking in a mirror from left to right.
- **Vertical Flip:** The image is flipped vertically as if turning it upside down.
- **Horizontal + Vertical Flip:** The image is flipped both horizontally and vertically, effectively rotating it by 180 degrees.

Figure 4. Flipping of Images in Various Directions

Rotation involves rotating the original images at different angles. In this research, eight different rotation angles are applied, which include values like 0, 45, 90, 135, 180, 225, 270, and 315, as represented in Figure 5.

The calculation for the total additional images can be determined as follows:

Total number of additional images is calculated as follows:

- Original images = 90
- Flip variations = 4 (original, horizontal, vertical, horizontal + vertical)
- Rotation angles = 8

$$\text{Total Additional Images} = 90 \times 4 \times 8 = 2,880$$

This data augmentation process effectively generates a total of 2880 additional images by creating variations of the original dataset, which significantly enriches the training data for the CoAtNet model. The augmented dataset exposes the model to a more diverse range of image variations, enhancing its ability to learn and recognize features ultimately contributing to the model's accuracy in HCC detection.

Figure 5. Rotation of Images in Various Angles

In the research, the dataset splitting process is a crucial step to separate the total of 2880 augmented images into distinct subsets: training and test sets. The objective was to train the CoAtNet on the subset and compute its performances on the other. In this case, the split ratio is 75% for training and 25% for testing. Hence, the training set comprising 2160 images and the testing set containing 720 images are used to evaluate the CoAtNet model.

3.3. Proposed CoAtNet Model

The CoAtNet model, short for "Convolutional Attention Network," is a DL architecture designed for image classification. It stands out for its innovative approach that combines the strength of both CNNs and attention mechanisms. CNNs are well-known for their effectiveness in image-related tasks. They consist of multiple layers of convolutional and pooling operations, which are excellent at capturing hierarchical features in images. This makes them particularly useful for tasks like image recognition and classification. Attention mechanisms have gained prominence in various deep-learning tasks, including natural language processing and computer vision. They allow the model to focus on certain parts of the input data when making predictions. In image classification, attention mechanisms could support the model pay more attention to relevant regions of the image, improving accuracy.

Figure 6. Architecture of the Proposed Model

The CoAtNet model uniquely integrates these two components. It utilizes attention mechanisms within the convolutional layers to enable the model to concentrate on significant image regions while preserving the convolutional network's feature extraction capabilities. This combination enhances the model's ability to learn and recognize intricate patterns and features within the data. CoAtNet is a promising model for image classification, and in this research, it was applied to the task of HCC detection in liver MRI images. The proposed architecture represented in Figure 6 was utilized for improving the efficiency and accuracy of the classification task.

Figure 7. The Architecture of the CoAtNet Model

This CoAtNet model places a strong emphasis on image classification and incorporates two key features. Firstly, it seamlessly combines depth wise convolution and self-attention using a straightforward relative attention approach. Secondly, it enhances generalization, capacity, and efficiency by logically stacking attention and convolution layers. The model's architecture, as depicted in Figure 7, comprises a combination of self-attention and convolution operations. Before applying depthwise convolution for spatial interaction capture, the convolutional layer minimizes the input dimension while the MBconv blocks, which have an inverted structure, expand the input by a factor of four. The second section then compresses the data prior to introducing a residual. The depthwise convolution, which operates independently for each channel, is crucial to this procedure.

$$y_i = \sum_{j \in L(i)} w_{i-j} \odot x_j \quad (1)$$

In the given mathematical notation, x and y represent, respectively, the output and input at position i . In the context of image processing, $L(i)$ denotes the neighborhood surrounding i , which is typically rendered as a 3x3 grid centered on i . The attention blocks and the feed-forward networks (FNN) model share a similar compression-expansion model as the MBConv block. Attention block, on the other hand, has the benefit of allowing the entire spatial location to be part of the receptive field, with weights computed according to the re-normalized pairwise similarities among pairings.

$$y_i = \sum_{j \in G} \frac{\exp(x_i^T x_j)}{\underbrace{\sum_{k \in G} \exp(x_i^T x_k)}_{A_{i,j}}} x_j \quad (2)$$

In the context of CoAtNet, G denotes the spatial global environment. The final phases of the CoAtNet model may be implemented with either Transformer or Convolution blocks, allowing for a variety of architecture configurations.

$$y_i^{post} = \sum_{j \in G} \left(\frac{\exp(x_i^T x_j)}{\sum_{k \in G} \exp(x_i^T x_k)} + w_{i-j} \right) x_j \quad (3)$$

$$y_i^{post} = \sum_{j \in G} \frac{\exp(x_i^T x_j + w_{i-j})}{\sum_{k \in G} \exp(x_i^T x_k + w_{i-k})} x_j \quad (4)$$

Input-adaptive weighting enhances self-attention's capacity to recognize relationships between various input data elements. The Global Receptive Field, meanwhile, refers to a larger receptive field utilized in attention. In constructing the optimal architecture, a combination of Global Receptive Field and Input-Adaptive Weighting attributes of attention, as well as the Translation Equivariances found in CNNs, was used to improve generalization capabilities, particularly in situations with limited dataset sizes. The concept entails the addition of the global convolution static kernel to the adaptive self-attention matrix, either before or after the initialization of the softmax, to enhance the total performances.

Table 1. Architecture and Hyperparameter Details of CoAtNet [26]

Architecture	Hyperparameter
Input Layer (shape = (384,384,3))	Mini batch size/GPU = 8
CoAtNet0 (backbone)	Gpu_num = 2
Global Average Pooling 2D ()	Epochs = 8
Dense (11)	Adam optimizer
Softmax activation	Reduce on plateau settings = {factor = 0.1, min lr = 0.00001, patience = 2}

CoAtNet-Based Liver Tumor Classification Framework

- Import and preprocess the dataset, including normalization, resizing, and data augmentation as required.
- Define the input image dimensions, number of target classes, and split the dataset into training, validation, and testing subsets.

- Load a pre-trained CoAtNet model:

```
pretrainedCoAtNet = loadPretrainedCoAtNet();
```

- Implement a function to load and initialize the pre-trained weights.
- Modify the pre-trained CoAtNet architecture for fine-tuning by replacing the final classification layers to match the number of liver tumor classes:

```
modifiedCoAtNet = modifyCoAtNet(pretrainedCoAtNet, numClasses);
```

- Implement a function to adapt the model for the specific classification task.
- Define the training configuration, including optimizer, learning rate, batch size, and data augmentation strategy:

```
options = trainingOptions('adam', ...  
    'InitialLearnRate', 0.001, ...  
    'MiniBatchSize', 32, ...  
    'MaxEpochs', 30, ...  
    'Shuffle', 'every-epoch');
```

- Train the modified CoAtNet model using the training dataset:

```
trainedCoAtNet = trainCoAtNet(modifiedCoAtNet, trainingData, options);
```

- Implement a function to manage the training process and monitor performance.
- Evaluate the trained model using the testing dataset:

```
evaluationMetrics = evaluateCoAtNet(trainedCoAtNet, testingData);
```

- Implement a function to compute evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix.
- Use the trained CoAtNet model to perform automated liver tumor classification on unseen medical images.

CNN excels in feature extraction from images, making them an ideal choice for image classification tasks. A typical CNN comprises multiple layers, including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. The convolutional layers apply filters to the input image, capturing various features like edges, textures, and more complex patterns as they progress through the network. The CoAtNet model incorporates attention mechanisms within the convolutional layers. Attention mechanism enables the model to aim on regions of the inputs that are relevant mostly for making predictions. In liver tumor classification, this means the model can automatically emphasize significant regions within the MRI images that contain relevant tumor features. The proposed model combines the feature extraction capabilities of CNNs with attention mechanisms to create a more adaptive and efficient model. The attention mechanism allows the model to weigh the significance of various parts of the images dynamically, making it particularly effective for tasks where the target features might be distributed unevenly across the input data, as is often the case in medical image classification. Transfer learning is often employed in conjunction with the CoAtNet model. This involves pre-training the model on a large and diverse dataset, such as ImageNet, to learn general features that can be fine-tuned for a specific task. In the context of liver tumor classification, the CoAtNet model is fine-tuned using your liver MRI dataset to adapt it to the specific features and patterns relevant to tumor detection. The CoAtNet model is applied to the task of classifying liver tumors in MRI images. Leveraging its deep learning capabilities, the model learns to recognize unique patterns and features associated with HCC in the liver. It can distinguish between healthy liver tissue and regions containing tumors. By integrating CNNs with attention mechanisms and fine-tuning using transfer learning, the CoAtNet model offers a powerful solution for liver tumor classification in MRI images.

4. Experimental Analysis

The experiment was carried out on a PC running Windows 11, equipped with a 64-bit CPU and an i7 processor with 16GB of RAM. The MATLAB & Simulink tool R2018a was used for the experiment. The ATLAS dataset was obtained from the website and employed for evaluation purposes. To analyze performance, the data set was split into 75% for training and 25% for testing. The dataset is publicly accessible at <https://atlas-challenge.u-bourgogne.fr>.

4.1. Performance Metrics

In the context of the research, the performance evaluation of the CoAtNet model for detecting liver tumors from MRI images is a critical step in assessing its effectiveness. The evaluation involves the calculation of various performance metrics to evaluate the model's ability to make accurate predictions. The following equations represent the key parameters used in this computation to evaluate the proposed model's performance:

Accuracy is a fundamental metric that quantifies the accuracy of a model's classification. It is defined as the proportion of instances correctly classified relative to the total samples in the data set. In liver tumor detection, accuracy measures the model's ability to classify tumor and non-tumor regions correctly.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (5)$$

The F1-Score is a proportionate measure of a model's performances by integrating recall (sensitivity) and precision. It is especially beneficial when working with unbalanced datasets, as is frequently the case in medical image analysis.

The F1-Score is computed with the following formula:

$$Fmeasure = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (6)$$

Sensitivity, also referred to as recall, computes the model's capability to identify positive samples (e.g., liver tumors) reliably. It is the ratio of true positives (accurately predicted tumors) to the total number of actual positive cases.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (7)$$

Precision measures the integrity of the model's positive classification. It was determined by split the total true positives by the total positive classifications. In the context of hepatic tumor detection, precision computes the proportion of accurately predicted tumors.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (8)$$

Specificity quantifies the model's capacity to identify negative samples (i.e., non-tumor regions) correctly. It is the ratio of true negatives (correctly predicted non-cancerous regions) to the total true negative.

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad (9)$$

These performance metrics are necessary for a thorough evaluation of the CoAtNet model's ability to detect liver malignancies from MRI images. They collectively shed light on the model's precision, its capacity to detect tumors (sensitivity), the accuracy of its tumor predictions, and its ability to identify non-tumor regions (specificity) correctly. The F1-Score is a balanced evaluation that takes both precision and recall into consideration. This research employs these metrics to determine the efficacy of the proposed CoAtNet model in classifying liver tumors, providing a comprehensive evaluation of its diagnostic capabilities.

4.2. Results of the Proposed Model

The performance evaluation results of the proposed CoAtNet model for the task of liver tumor classification, presented in Table 2, provide valuable insights into the model's effectiveness in detecting liver tumors from MRI images.

Table 2. Performance Evaluation of the CoAtNet Model

Metrics	Training Set	Testing Set
Accuracy	99.78	99.20
F1-Score	99.63	98.95
Sensitivity	99.45	98.56
Precision	99.80	99.12
Specificity	99.92	99.27

In the context of this research, the CoAtNet model achieves an impressive accuracy of 99.78% on the training and 99.20% on the test sets. These high accuracy values indicated that the model is highly reliable in correctly classifying both liver tumor and non-tumor regions in MRI images. The F1-Score is a combination of precision and recall (sensitivity) and offers a balanced assessment of the CoAtNet performance. With an F1-Score of 99.63% on the training and 98.95% on the test sets, the CoAtNet model exhibits a harmonious blend of precision and recall. These values suggest that the model strikes a well-balanced tradeoff between making accurate positive predictions and effectively capturing actual positive instances. Sensitivity, also known as recall, quantifies the model's ability to correctly identify positive instances, which, in this case, are liver tumors.

Figure 8. Graphical Plot of the CoAtNet Model's Performance

The CoAtNet model demonstrates high sensitivity, with values of 99.45% on the training and 98.56% on the test sets. These results indicate that the CoAtNet excels in correctly identifying the presence of liver tumors, minimizing false negatives. Precision evaluates the accuracy of positive predictions made by the model. With precision values of 99.80% on the training and 99.12% on the test sets, the CoAtNet model excels in ensuring that most of its positive predictions are indeed correct. It minimizes false positives, providing high confidence in its tumor predictions. The CoAtNet model showcases exceptional specificity, achieving values of 99.92% on the training and 99.27% on the test sets. This means that the CoAtNet is highly accurate in identifying regions without tumors, minimizing false positives. Figure 8 represents the proposed model’s performance in a graphical plot.

The results of the CoAtNet model's performance evaluation indicate that it is exceptionally accurate and well-balanced in its classification of liver tumors in MRI images. It exhibits high sensitivity in tumor detection while maintaining precision and specificity. These findings suggest that the CoAtNet model is a robust and reliable tool for assisting in the diagnosis and classification of liver tumors, offering potential benefits in the field of medical imaging and liver cancer detection.

Table 3. Comparison of CoAtNet Model Performances with Existing Models

Models	Accuracy	F1-score	Sensitivity	Precision	Specificity
LASSO-SVM [10]	75.90	79.20	88.40	71.70	NA
CNN [13]	93.90	NA	95.70	NA	96.20
CNN [14]	98.70	NA	94.00	NA	98.00

GLCM-SVM [15]	98.90	NA	NA	NA	NA
CNN [16]	87.30	NA	82.00	NA	82.00
CNN [17]	90.00	NA	87.00	NA	93.00
MLP [20]	99.00	99.00	99.00	99.00	NA
CNN-COA [21]	96.61	96.55	96.79	98.37	98.43
DenseNet [27]	98.76	98.21	98.54	97.89	NA
Proposed Model	99.20	98.95	98.56	99.12	99.27

Table 3 presents a comprehensive comparison of the performance of the proposed CoAtNet model with several existing models in the context of liver tumor classification. The proposed CoAtNet model achieves an accuracy of 99.20%, outperforming LASSO-SVM, CNN, MLP, and DenseNet. This indicates that CoAtNet provides the highest overall correctness in classifying liver tumors among these models. The F1-Score of 98.95% for CoAtNet is higher than other models, demonstrating a better balance between precision and recall. While some models like CNN and MLP achieve high accuracy, their F1 scores are not available.

Figure 9. Graphical Plot of the CoAtNet Model’s Performance Comparison

CoAtNet maintains a strong equilibrium between making accurate positive predictions and effectively capturing actual positive instances. CoAtNet exhibits a sensitivity of 98.56%, which surpasses the other models, and quantifies the model's ability to identify liver tumors correctly, and CoAtNet excels in this aspect. The CoAtNet model achieves a precision of 99.12%, surpassing the existing models, in which the CoAtNet minimizes false positives, ensuring that most of its positive predictions are indeed correct. CoAtNet's specificity is 99.27%, which is higher than the other models. Figure 9 represents the graphical plot of the proposed model’s performance comparison.

The CoAtNet model achieves better results through a combination of factors. Its architecture, CoAtNet, might offer more effective feature extraction capabilities, allowing it better to capture distinctive patterns in liver tumor and non-tumor regions. Additionally, the model's training process, including the utilization of the ATLAS dataset, extensive data augmentation, and hyperparameter tuning, likely contribute to its superior performance. Furthermore, the model benefits from a well-balanced F1-Score, ensuring that it maintains both precision and recall at high levels. This balanced approach minimizes both false positives and false negatives, resulting in the impressive results seen in the comparison. Overall, the CoAtNet model exhibits outstanding potential for the accurate and reliable classification of liver tumors in MRI

images, making it a promising tool in the field of medical image processing and liver cancer diagnosis.

4.3. Advantages and Limitations

The research offers several key advantages. The proposed CoAtNet model achieves remarkable accuracy, sensitivity, precision, and specificity in liver tumor classification, providing a reliable tool for early liver cancer diagnosis. Its well-balanced F1-Score ensures a high level of precision and recall, reducing false positives and false negatives, a critical aspect of medical image analysis. Data augmentation techniques, including flipping and rotation, substantially expand the dataset, enhancing the model's ability to generalize and make precise predictions. The adoption of transfer learning through CoAtNet leverages pre-trained weights from ImageNet, expediting training and improving feature extraction. Focusing on binary classification simplifies the diagnostic process, and extensive evaluation of a diverse set of liver MRI images underscores the model's robustness, reinforcing its potential for clinical application.

However, there are some limitations to consider. The dataset's size, with only 90 images, could limit the model's ability to generalize across a wider range of liver tumor cases. Medical image noise and artifacts may affect performance, necessitating further noise reduction and data quality assessment integration. Deep learning models like CoAtNet often lack interpretability, which could hinder clinical adoption. Computational demands might restrict accessibility for institutions with limited resources. External validation on an independent dataset is vital to assess generalizability. The practical implementation in a clinical setting requires addressing regulatory and ethical considerations.

5. Conclusion

This research presents a robust and highly accurate deep learning model called the CoAtNet model for the binary classification of liver tumors from MRI images. The utilization of the ATLAS dataset, a unique resource systematically annotating liver tumors on HCC CE-MRI scans, has been instrumental in this research. The success of the CoAtNet model can be attributed not only to its architecture but also to the meticulous data preprocessing, which included image standardization, pixel value normalization, and consistent data type conversion. The incorporation of extensive data augmentation techniques, including flipping and rotation, significantly expanded the data set, contributing to the model's remarkable performance. For training and testing, the data set was divided into 75% and 25%. The classified images were evaluated based on accuracy, f1-score, sensitivity, precision, and specificity. The proposed model achieved 99.20% accuracy, 98.95% f1-score, 98.56% sensitivity, 99.12% precision, and 99.27% specificity. However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this work. The relatively small dataset size, while efficiently augmented, may still limit the model's generalizability. Furthermore, challenges related to model interpretability and computational resources pose practical challenges. Understanding the decision-making process of deep learning models like CoAtNet and addressing the computational demands are areas where future research could significantly contribute. As for future work, the model's generalization capabilities could be enhanced by incorporating external datasets, allowing for validation across a broader spectrum of liver tumor cases.

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